

Section: Current international economic relations in social responsibility context.

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GROWTH PROSPECTS OF CHINESE INBOUND TOURISM AND ITS SOCIAL-ECONOMIC IMPACT ON UKRAINE

On the modern stage of development of global economy international tourism has become an important driver of globalization and socio-economic development both on supranational and national level. Developing and transitional countries can benefit from international tourism because it provides workplaces, additional foreign exchange earnings, establish intercultural and economic linkages between countries that can lead to economic growth, modernization of infrastructure and resolution of various social issues [1].

According to World Bank in 2015 global expenditures on international tourism amounted to 1.371 trillion US dollars. The largest tourist market in the world is People's Republic of China (PRC). During the last ten years demand on tourist services – both domestic and international – skyrocketed in China which leads to significant increase in number of outbound destinations (in 2007 some 40.9540 million Chinese traveled overseas, in 2016 this number grow to more than 135 million). According to United Nations World Tourism Organization in 2016 Chinese citizens spend more than a \$261 billion on international travel. Currently tourists from PRC are primarily interested in Thailand, South Korea, Japan, Indonesia, Singapore and United States. However, ceaseless rise of PRC's middle class strongly implies that this trend will continue and numbers of Chinese visitors will soon exceed absorptive capacities of popular tourist destinations which will force Chinese to explore alternatives. For Ukraine even a small fracture of tourists flow from China can pose a significant opportunity to

revitalize its tourist industry [2; 3]. Chinese tourism also proves to be relatively profitable for Eastern European countries, according to Central Statistical Office of Poland Chinese tourists have much higher average expenditures per person than tourists from other countries: 7,872 Polish Zlotys (or 2,059.87 US Dollars) per person, that is 40% higher than average expenditure by tourists from USA (5,603 zloty per person) [4].

In 2016 to attract tourists Ukraine significantly simplified entrance of foreigners by allowing receiving visa upon arrival at the airports in capital city of Kiev and sea-resort city of Odessa. According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine 19,599 persons from China had visited Ukraine in 2016 which is 30.6% more than in the previous year (13,602 visitors). This number is higher than number of Chinese visitors in Belarus (1,579) but significantly lower than in Poland (some 97 thousand) and virtually non-existent compared to Russia (1,288,720) [5; 6]. In order to lure in Chinese tourists Ukrainian business require innovative approach that will take full account of the preferences of the people of PRC.

According to PRC's own national statistics and the experience of other recipient countries tourists and visitors from China are mainly interested in shopping (mostly in Western European countries), sightseeing and visiting historical landmarks (both European, Soviet and related to China), recreational and environmental tourism, culinary tourism and 'thanatourism' (visiting places associated with grief or tragedy) [6; 7]. Potentially Ukraine is attractive to Chinese visitors in literally every branch of tourism (see table 1).

Notable advantage of Ukraine compared to Poland or Russia is the mix of European and Soviet historical and cultural heritage. Increase of inbound tourists from China can become an effective way to monetize Soviet era historical legacy and at the same time effectively apply decommunization laws. Various individual monuments can be preserved and moved in theme parks

aimed at foreign, particularly Chinese and Vietnamese tourists. Creation of such theme parks can provide additional support for institutions for preservation of historical legacy and lower social tensions caused by the debates around the fate of Soviet era monuments and landmarks.

Because of the air pollution problem in all major cities of China natural environment is one of the most important factors for Chinese tourists. Sparsely populated Western regions of Ukraine is especially perspective considering lack of industry and little to none urbanization. Food security is also a major concern in China. The growing demand for high quality GMO-free products cannot be satisfied by foreign producers because government restricts import of food to ensure the security and independence of domestic market. Dissatisfied with their daily ration Chinese middle class is turning to culinary tourism (15.4% of outbound Chinese tourists are interested specifically in food) [6]. For Chinese urban citizens homegrown food is an expensive luxury while in Ukraine it is usually a sign of poverty or subsistence farming in remote undeveloped regions. By combining both outdoor and culinary tourist flows it is possible to open small restaurants with homegrown and home-cooked food near every major landmark or national park. Such enterprises can significantly improve the welfare of local individual farmers and households and provide workplaces thus ensuring the social security of remote villages.

The important issue of China-Ukraine tourism cooperation is language. Chinese native speakers and the number of Ukrainians fluent in Chinese are insignificant. Because of this Ukraine lacks China-friendly venues, hotels and restaurants with the signs written in Chinese, guides and staff workers who speak the language. The gravity of situation is exacerbated by the fact that PRC is a major trade partner of Ukraine in Asia with a turnover of 6.5 billions of US dollars in bilateral trade. Chinese are known to be skilled negotiators in trade and this is why language and cultural issue must become national priority in Ukraine-Chinese foreign relations.

Table 1. Possible destinations and attractions of Chinese tourists in Ukraine

Branch of tourism:		Location in Ukraine particularly fitting the description:	Reason why location is attractive specifically to Chinese tourists:
1.	Recreational tourism.	Carpathian mountains.	Good air quality, relatively low prices.
2.	Historical tourism:	Various landmarks, monuments and sites dedicated to Ukrainian history from ancient to modern eras, including:	
	2.1. Ancient sites	Khortitsa island.	Historical sites in any way related with the Silk Road.
	2.2. European history.	Lviv (historical center of the city); Kamianets-Podilskyi fortress.	Landmarks of Medieval and Imperial Europe.
	2.3. Soviet history.	Dnieper Hydroelectric Station, Zaporozhye.	Landmarks and industry of USSR.
3.	Culinary tourism.	Various remote villages and hamlets in all regions of Ukraine.	Home produced food and traditional cuisine, GMO-free.
4.	Movie-inspired tourism.	Kosiv National Park, Lviv.	Locations featured in popular Chinese films.
5.	Thanatourism.	Babi Yar, Kiev; Chernobyl city and zone of alienation.	Worldwide places related to tragedy and grief.

Source: systemized data from research of various scholars

Conclusion. Increase in inbound tourism from China can provide various social benefits for citizens of Ukraine ranging from new workplaces to preservation of historical legacy. To insure the growth rate of inbound tourists from China Ukrainian tourist companies must ensure government support to optimize the advantages of national tourist market and minimize negative factors (see table 2).

Table 2. Pros and cons of visiting Ukraine for Chinese tourists

Positive factors of Ukrainian tourism:	Negative factors of Ukrainian tourism:
Geographical location between Russian and Europe which provide unique mix of cultures and lifestyles; various historical landmarks of different time periods and cultures; air quality and national environment (in Western regions); low exchange rate of national currency.	Ongoing military conflict in Eastern regions; political instability; service and facilities for tourists are underdeveloped and outdated; not enough staff and guides fluent in Chinese language and culture.

Source: author's own conclusions based on previous similar research material [8]

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